

Supplementary Material to:

Heat Pump Noise: Scoping Overview of Emission Characteristics and Systematic Review of Human Effects

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Table S1. Equipment used to measure the sound emissions of the air source heat pump (ASHP).

Device	Device name	Manufacturer	Origin
Microphone preamplifier 1-8	MV 220 P48	Mikrotech Gefell GmbH	Gefell, Germany
Microphone capsules 1-8	No. 4189	Brüel & Kjaer Sound & Vibration Measurements A/S	Naerum, Denmark
Microphone preamplifier 9-13	MA 220	NTi Audio AG	Schaan, Liechtenstein
Microphone capsules 9-13	MC 230 A	NTi Audio AG	Schaan, Liechtenstein
Data acquisition device (two devices coupled)	896mk3 Hybrid	MOTU, Inc.	Cambridge, USA
Reference source	No. 4204	Brüel & Kjaer Sound & Vibration Measurements A/S	Naerum, Denmark

Table S2. Overview of search strings and search dates for each database, search platform, and additional information source.

Database	Date of Search	Search String (Field/Filter, if applicable)
Web of Science (Core Collection)	30.07.2025	((TS=("heat pump*")) AND TS=("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength")) AND TS=("annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR "noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability"))
SCOPUS	30.07.2025	(TITLE-ABS-KEY("heat pump*") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR "noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability"))
PubMed	30.07.2025	("heat pump*[Title/Abstract]) AND (noise[Title/Abstract] OR sound[Title/Abstract] OR exposure[Title/Abstract] OR acoust*[Title/Abstract] OR psychoacoust*[Title/Abstract] OR loud*[Title/Abstract] OR tone*[Title/Abstract] OR tonal*[Title/Abstract] OR sharpness[Title/Abstract] OR roughness[Title/Abstract] OR fluctuation strength[Title/Abstract]) AND (annoy*[Title/Abstract] OR disturb*[Title/Abstract] OR bother*[Title/Abstract] OR affective*[Title/Abstract] OR preference*[Title/Abstract] OR perception*[Title/Abstract] OR psychol*[Title/Abstract] OR psychiat*[Title/Abstract] OR health[Title/Abstract] OR acceptance*[Title/Abstract] OR "noise problem"[Title/Abstract] OR "community response"[Title/Abstract] OR complain*[Title/Abstract] OR "listening experiment"[Title/Abstract] OR "human response"[Title/Abstract] OR acceptability[Title/Abstract])
ProQuest Dissertation (via WOS)	30.07.2025	((TS=("heat pump*")) AND TS=("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength")) AND TS=("annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR

Database	Date of Search	Search String (Field/Filter, if applicable)
OpenAlex	30.07.2025	<p>"noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability")</p> <p>Filter: Title&Abstract: "heat pump*" AND ("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength") AND ("annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR "noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability")</p>
GoogleScholar	30.07.2025	<p>allintitle: noise OR sound OR exposure OR acoustics OR loudness OR sharpness OR roughness OR "fluctuation strength" OR annoyance OR disturb OR bother OR affective OR preference OR perception OR psychology OR health OR acceptance OR complain OR complaint OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR acceptability "heat pump"</p>
PsycInfo (via ProQuest)	31.07.2025	<p>TIABSU(("heat pump" OR "heat pumps") AND ("noise*" OR "sound" OR "sounds" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength") AND ("annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR "noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability"))</p>
LIVIVO	31.07.2025	<p>Keyword: ("heat pump" OR "heat pumps") AND (noise OR sound OR exposure OR acoust OR psychoacoust OR loud OR tone OR tonal OR sharpness OR roughness OR "fluctuation strength") AND (annoy OR disturb OR bother OR affective OR preference OR perception OR psychol OR psychi OR health OR acceptance OR "noise problem" OR "noise problems" OR "community response" OR complain OR "listening experiment" OR "listening experiments" OR "human response" OR "human responses" OR acceptability)</p>
GreenFile	31.07.2025	<p>AB ("heat pump*" AND ("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength") AND ("annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR</p>

Database	Date of Search	Search String (Field/Filter, if applicable)
TIB	05.08.2025	<p>"noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability"))</p> <p>(keyword:("heat pump*") AND keyword:("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength" OR "annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR "noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability")) OR (mainTitle:("heat pump*" AND ("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength" OR "annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR "noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability")) OR subTitle:("heat pump*" AND ("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength" OR "annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR "noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability")) OR alternativeTitle:("heat pump*" AND ("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength" OR "annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*" OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR "noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability"))))</p>
Dimensions	05.08.2025	<p>Title & Abstract: "heat pump*" AND ("noise*" OR "sound*" OR "exposure*" OR "acoust*" OR "psychoacoust*" OR "loud*" OR "tone*" OR "tonal*" OR "sharpness" OR "roughness" OR "fluctuation strength") AND ("annoy*" OR "disturb*" OR "bother*" OR "affective*" OR "preference*" OR "perception*"</p>

Database	Date of Search	Search String (Field/Filter, if applicable)
ICBEN Proceedings 1973–2023 (manually downloaded & screened)	31.07.2025	OR "psychol*" OR "psychi*" OR "health" OR "acceptance*" OR "noise problem" OR "community response" OR "complain*" OR "listening experiment" OR "human response" OR "acceptability") Search terms: "heat", "pump"

Table S3. Data extraction template with explanatory descriptions, topically structured.

Topic	Variables	Description
Bibliographic information	Title	Study title
	Year	Year of publication
	Author(s)	Author(s) of the study
	Document Type	Journal article, conference paper, report, etc.
	Retrieval Type	Retrieved via database search or manually (i.e., known literature, backwards citation search, etc.)
Exposure	LT/ST Exposure	Long-term or short-term exposure
	SPL	Reported sound pressure levels (or related metrics like psychoacoustics)
	Noise Sources	Type of heat pumps (ASHP, GSHP) and other investigated noise sources
	Stimuli	Generation of the used stimuli (e.g., recordings, auralizations)
	Background sound/Reference	If background noise was present/investigated and if reference sound was used (e.g., white noise)
Study Context & Design	Study design	Type of study (e.g., survey, lab study, etc.)
	Region	Country of study
	Population	Sample size and participant characteristics
	Aim	Research question, motivation, aim of the study
Outcomes & Analysis	Outcome(s)	Noise-related effects assessed
	Measurement method	Scales and/or instruments used
	Factors	Independent variables or modifiers investigated

Topic	Variables	Description
Risk of Bias & Study Quality (primary concerns specified per evidence type)	Statistical Methods	Statistical methods used for data analysis
	Results	Relevant (key) results pertaining to noise effects
	Sample representativeness	Representativeness of the study sample; Experimental: external validity (generalizability) Observational: selection bias, representativeness Predictive: plausibility and representativeness of input population
	Measurement validity	Appropriateness of outcome measurement; Experimental: validity of scales, blinding of assessors Observational: validity of tools, measurement misclassification Predictive: validity of predictors and outcomes
	Control of confounders	Control of confounding factors (e.g., background noise levels, dB); Experimental: randomization procedure, control group Observational: identification of key confounders, use of adjustment methods Predictive: model assumptions and adjustment, empirical validation
	Reporting completeness	Completeness of reporting (e.g., availability of critical information); Experimental: trial conduct transparency Observational: analytic transparency (methods, assumptions) Predictive: model transparency, missing data specification
	Bias assessment	Overall risk of bias (RoB) classification
Notes	Additional notes/justifications for RoB assessment	

Table S4. Stepwise decision rules for deriving overall risk-of-bias classifications.

Step	Question (Decision Criterion)	Decision
1	Are all domains low risk?	Yes → Overall Low No → go to 2
2	Are both critical domains low, and at most one non-critical domain moderate, with none high?	Yes → Overall Low No → go to 3
3	Is either critical domain high risk?	Yes → Overall High No → go to 4
4	Are two or more domains high risk?	Yes → Overall High No → go to 5
5	Are both critical domains moderate risk, and both remaining domains high risk?	Yes → Overall High No → Overall Moderate